

Narrative of Traditional Pot Making in Modern Benin Kingdom, Southern Nigeria

A Case Study of Two Potters in Okabere and Uselu Communities

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Abstract

Traditional pottery production in the Benin Kingdom represents one of the most enduring craft practices in Southern Nigeria. Despite processes of urbanisation and socio-economic change, communities such as Okabere and Uselu have retained elements of their ancestral pot-making traditions. This article presents a qualitative case study of two potter families in Okabere and Uselu, drawing on longitudinal fieldwork conducted between 2006 and 2023 to examine continuity, decline, and gendered transmission of the craft. The study, a collaboration between a Nigerian ceramicist and an American art historian, documents and interprets the practices of these potters over nearly two decades. Employing ethnographic fieldwork, practice-led research, and visual documentation, the research analyses clay sourcing, preparation, production, baking, surface finishing, and distribution. Particular attention is given to differences in clay maturation, firing strategies, and market orientation between the two communities, and to the matrilineal transmission of skills within the Onaiwu family in Okabere and the threatened transmission line in Uselu. Findings highlight both continuity and decline in pottery traditions, shaped by broader dynamics of modernisation, resource constraints, and generational change. The analysis also links these local trajectories to wider African pottery scholarship and to discourses on intangible cultural heritage, emphasising women's central role as custodians of the craft. The article argues for safeguarding these practices as living heritage and for recognising their pedagogical and creative value in contemporary art education and cultural policy.

Key words: Traditional pottery; Benin Kingdom; Okabere; Uselu; qualitative case study; gendered craft; intangible cultural heritage.

INTRODUCTION

The Benin Kingdom, located in present-day Edo State, South-South Nigeria, has long been celebrated for its cultural and artistic achievements, ranging from bronze casting to ivory carving (Eyo, 1990; Ben-Amos, 1995; Plankensteiner, 2007). Less commonly emphasised, but no less significant, are the pottery traditions that have flourished in rural and semi-urban communities. Pottery making, as both material culture and embodied knowledge, offers insights into the lived realities of communities, their histories, and their adaptive strategies in the face of change. This paper explores the narratives and practices of traditional pot making in Okabere and Uselu communities, situating them within the broader context of contemporary Benin. The study, which began in 2006 and extended through repeat visits over two decades, provides longitudinal insight into the survival of these craft practices amid urbanisation, shifting economies, and changing cultural values. The collaborative nature of this research—between a Nigerian studio-based ceramicist and an American art historian—offers a dual lens. While the ceramicist brings practice-led insight into the technical and material aspects of pot making, the art historian situates these practices within broader discourses of heritage and cultural representation. Together, this approach aligns with arguments by Denzin and Lincoln (2018) regarding the value of multi-perspectival qualitative inquiry. This article presents a case study of two potter families in Okabere and Uselu communities, using their practices to explore continuity, decline, and gendered transmission of traditional pottery in the modern Benin Kingdom. The study aims to: document in detail the processes of clay sourcing, forming, firing, and surface finishing; situate these practices within the long historical and gendered context of Benin pottery; and analyse the sustainability of the craft under contemporary socio-economic pressures between 2006 and 2023.

Literature Review

In a literature review of pottery in African art and culture, pottery has historically been one of the most widespread and significant crafts across African societies. It is both functional—providing vessels for storage, cooking, and ritual use—and symbolic, embodying cosmological and social meanings (Gosselain, 1992; Sterner, 1989). In Nigeria, pottery traditions are diverse, ranging from works in the north linked to the Nok culture, dating from approximately 1500 BCE to 1 BCE (Franke, 2014), to more recent studio pottery associated with Ladi Kwali in the Abuja area, itself rooted in the region's historic practice, and to the south-western Yoruba regions, notably the terracottas of ancient Ife and Owo (Eyo & Willett, 1982). In Edo State, scholarly attention has often centred on the Benin bronzes (Dark, 1973; Ben-Amos, 1995) and broader Benin court arts traditions (Plankensteiner, 2007), with pottery remaining under-researched. Yet, pottery in Benin provides crucial evidence of continuity from the era of the Ogisos (circa 800 AD) to the present day, revealing the lived experiences of communities often overlooked in canonical art histories.

Beyond Nigerian studies on pottery as material culture and intangible heritage, related research in Ghana and elsewhere in Africa underscores the social and ritual importance of women's pottery and its changing functions. Asante, Adjei, and Opoku-Asare examine women's pottery in Kpando and its socio-cultural meanings, while Adjei and colleagues and Iddrisu and co-authors document the roles, functions, and decorative techniques of

traditional pottery in different Ghanaian contexts. Comparative process-oriented studies, such as Haron and Abd Mutalib on Malay heritage pottery and Okwoche and Okonkwo on contemporary pottery in Yala, Nigeria, further highlight how local technologies and production systems adapt to modern markets, providing a wider frame within which to situate the Benin case.

A review of urbanisation and the decline of craft traditions in Africa shows that several scholars, Anthony King (2006), among others, have documented this phenomenon. Indeed, a simple search of the phrase "decline of traditional crafts linked to urbanization in Nigeria" brings up numerous articles. In relation to pottery, the proliferation of factory-made containers—plastic, aluminium, and enamelware—has reduced the domestic demand for earthenware pots. This trend is evident in Okabere and Uselu, where younger generations increasingly seek metropolitan employment rather than craft-based livelihoods. Projecting pottery culture in Africa as intangible cultural heritage, UNESCO's 2003 Convention for the Safeguarding of Intangible Cultural Heritage underscores the importance of preserving living traditions, including craftsmanship. Pottery, as a practice transmitted orally and experientially, epitomises intangible heritage. Scholars such as Kurin (2004) and Blake (2009) argue that safeguarding requires both documentation and community-based strategies for continuity.

The material culture and practice-led perspectives of the study draw on material culture approaches, particularly Miller's (2005) view of artefacts as mediators of social relations, and Tilley's (2006) phenomenological interpretations of craft. Additionally, practice-led research offers a methodology for artists and artisans to use their own practice as a mode of inquiry (Candy & Edmonds, 2018). This is particularly relevant given one author's expertise in ceramics, allowing for grounded interpretative insights. While documenting contemporary practice, this study also addresses two critical, interconnected questions raised by the longitudinal data: first, the deep historical roots of Benin pottery, which anchor it as one of the region's most enduring art forms, and second, the gendered nature of the craft, which has established women as its primary custodians for generations, situating the modern potters of Okabere and Uselu within this enduring legacy.

Historical and Gendered Context of the Craft

While the royal bronze casts of Benin have garnered global acclaim, the tradition of pottery represents a deeper, more ubiquitous, and arguably more ancient artistic lineage. Archaeological evidence suggests that pottery production in the region of the Benin Kingdom dates back to the era of the Ogisos, the first dynasty of Benin, circa 800 AD (Dark, 1973). Excavations around the Benin area have revealed pottery shards with distinctive decorative motifs and firing techniques that show a clear technological and stylistic continuity with forms produced in communities like Okabere and Uselu today. Unlike the courtly art of bronze, which was centralised and regulated by the Oba's guild system, pottery was a decentralised, domestic craft, flourishing in villages and serving both the everyday and ritual needs of the people. This enduring practice positions pottery not as a minor art, but as a vital archaeological and cultural record, offering a tangible link to the pre-royal, quotidian life of the Benin people and demonstrating an unbroken thread of material culture that has survived for over a millennium.

The Female Custodians of the Craft: A Socio-Cultural Explanation

The pottery tradition in the Benin Kingdom is predominantly, and in many communities exclusively, a female vocation. This gendered specialisation is not arbitrary but is deeply embedded in the socio-cultural and economic fabric of the society. Several interrelated factors explain this phenomenon:

1. **Division of Labour and Proximity to the Home:** Traditionally, pottery making was integrated with other domestic responsibilities primarily managed by women. The entire process from clay preparation to firing could be conducted in or near the homestead, allowing women to simultaneously manage childcare, cooking, and other household duties. This proximity made it a compatible and sustainable income-generating activity within the female domain of work.
2. **Matrilineal Knowledge Transmission:** The skill of pot making is a quintessential example of intangible cultural heritage, passed down orally and through practical apprenticeship from mother to daughter. As observed in this study, the practice within the Onaiwu family, where knowledge flows from Madam Dora Onaiwu to her daughter, Mrs. Patience Iziegbe, exemplifies this matrilineal transmission line. This system ensures the preservation of technical knowledge and aesthetic styles within specific female lineages, reinforcing the craft's identity as women's knowledge (Ekpo, 2013; Osariyekemwen & Eweka, 2016).
3. **Symbolic and Ritual Associations:** In many West African cultures, including Benin, there exists a potent symbolic connection between women and the earth, fertility, and creation. The process of forming a pot from formless clay—a substance sourced from the earth—and giving it life through fire is seen as a metaphor for childbirth and creation. This symbolic resonance further legitimised and naturalised pottery as a female craft. While our informants emphasised the utilitarian aspects of their work, this deeper cultural undercurrent historically sanctioned their role as potters.
4. **Economic Autonomy:** Pottery provided women with a crucial source of economic independence. The ability to produce and market functional wares gave women control over a segment of the local economy, a dynamic that continues, albeit on a smaller scale, in modern markets like the Oba Market in Benin City.

While urbanisation and shifting economic opportunities are challenging this long-standing tradition, as noted in our findings, its historical roots as a female-preserved craft are deep, reflecting a complex interplay of practical necessity, cultural symbolism, and matrilineal heritage.

METHODOLOGY

Approach

The study employed a qualitative, ethnographic approach (Creswell & Poth, 2018). Data collection involved:

1. Fieldwork conducted intermittently from 2006 to 2023 in Okabere and Uselu, including participant observation, interviews, and documentation of pottery practices.
2. Visual documentation, comprising photographs that captured processes from clay preparation to surface finishing.
3. Collaborative interpretation, combining the perspectives of a practitioner-researcher and an art historian.
4. Archival research into existing literature on Nigerian pottery and Benin art traditions.

Study Area: Okabere and Uselu

Okabere is a semi-rural community within Ikpoba-Okha Local Government Area of Edo State, approximately 8.1 km from the centre of Benin City. It forms part of a wider LGA with an estimated population of about 195,874 people and a mixed livelihood base that includes farming, petty trading, civil service, and craft production. The community has basic road access, local markets, and multiple water sources, and is culturally integrated into broader Benin Kingdom festivals and mixed Christian, Islamic, and traditional religious practices.

Uselu is a semi-urban community in Egor Local Government Area, about 10.4 km from central Benin City, with an estimated population of roughly 500,000 people in the wider LGA. Its economy is strongly oriented towards trading and services, with limited craft production, and it shares similar infrastructural and religious features with Okabere while being more closely connected to metropolitan markets in Benin City. There has been some documentation of pottery production in both these areas throughout the 20th century (Thomas 1910; Willett & Connah 1969; Leith-Ross 1970).

Selection of Focal Potters

The study focused on two potter families whose members were the only documented traditional potters in their respective communities during the main period of fieldwork. In Okabere, the research centred on the late Madam Dora Onaiwu (1944–2024) and her daughter, Mrs Patience Iziegbe, who exemplify a matrilineal line of potters and a practice that emphasises clay maturation, multi-stage firing, and intergenerational knowledge transmission (*Figs. 1 & 2*).

Figure 1: Madam Dora Onaiwu (1944–2024), a potter and participant in the study, is at work in her compound, Okabere village, Benin City. *Photo: Jean Borgatti, 30 November 2015.*

Figure 2: Mrs. Patience Iziegbe, daughter of the late Madam Dora Onaiwu and a practicing potter in Okabere village, Benin City, also participated in the study, *Photo: Jean Borgatti, 30 November 2015.*

In Uselu, the principal practitioner studied was Madam Pat Osaro (b. 1960) (*Fig. 3*), whose production is oriented toward supplying major markets in Benin City and whose working methods involve more direct use of freshly kneaded clay, intensive foot-kneading, and round stacking of bowls for open firing.

Figure 3: Madam Pat Osaro, a participant in the study, produces small clay bowls in her compound at Egua-iyoba, Uselu, Benin City. *Photo: Jean Borgatti, 12 November 2015.*

These two cases were selected because together they illustrate both continuity and variation in techniques, firing strategies, and market orientation within a shrinking field of practice, allowing for cautious comparison and contrast rather than broad generalisation. In what follows, the practices of these two potter families are compared and contrasted to show how shared Benin techniques are adapted differently in a semi-rural context (Okabere) and a semi-urban context (Uselu), rather than to claim broad generalisation beyond these cases.

Field Chronology

Fieldwork was conducted intermittently between 2006 and 2023 in Okabere and Uselu. Initial visits in 2006 ran from April to November on a bi-monthly basis, linked to student work-experience and industrial training programmes, and were followed by intermittent return visits between 2007 and 2014. An intensive documentation phase took place between February and November 2015, during which the photographs reproduced in this article were taken, and this was complemented by shorter follow-up visits in 2017, 2019, and a final status-check visit in June 2023. Together, these visits provide longitudinal insight into the trajectories of the two potter families over nearly two decades.

Ethical Clearance and Informed Consent

The research did not receive formal institutional ethical approval but followed standard ethical procedures, including informed consent from participants.

Informed consent was secured from participants, notably the Onaiwu and Osaro families, whose practices form the core case studies..

FINDINGS

Clay Preparation

Production The potters sourced clay from the Ovia region in Edo State, specifically from Oduna, Igo, and Ugbine, located approximately 26 km from Okabere and 32 km from Uselu. The clay, known locally as Obue Ovia clay, is supplied by local merchants four times per year at a cost of ₦100,000 per batch in 2023. This clay source has been in use since ancient times and is also utilised by the Fine Arts Department of the University of Benin and a Chinese floor tile company in Benin City.

The Obue Ovia clay possesses a brown-green colour, fine texture, high plasticity, and contains organic matter and visible brown iron oxide tones, making it highly suitable for hand building. Clay preparation began with shredding clay balls into fine bits using a cutlass, followed by slaking in water for over a week. The addition of sieved erosion sand reduced plasticity and improved workability. At Okabere, Madam Dora Onaiwu preferred to leave kneaded clay to mature by stamping lumps against the walls of her mud house, a practice that developed the clay's workability over time (*Figs. 4-7*).

(L) Figure 4: Balls of clay bought from suppliers for pottery making stacked against wall at Okabere, Benin City. 26 November 2015. **(R) Figure 5:** Crushed pieces of clay ready for soaking in water. Okabere, Benin City. 9 July 2015. Photos: Jean Borgatti

Figure 6: (L) Clay soaking in plastic bucket to soften into paste. Okabere. Benin City. 9 July 2015.

Figure 7: (R) Softened clay balls stamped onto earthen wall to ensure clay hardens to a state suitable for Okabere potters to use. 26 November 2015.

In contrast, at Uselu, Mrs Pat Osaro often worked directly with freshly kneaded clay for smaller vessels, employing foot-kneading to mix sand with clay (*Fig.8*) and open up the clay pores, creating a material that served for forming small bowls.

Techniques

Potters used broken pot shards, or today, shallow enamel bowls, as temporary bases on which to build new forms (*Figs. 9 -10*). They hand built vessels through coiling, paddling with kidney-shaped wooden tools, pinching, and stretching (*Figs. 11-12*). The process demanded rhythmic dexterity developed over years of apprenticeship. Unique rims and necks were fashioned by steady finger movements using wet plantain leaves to achieve near-perfect finishing (*Fig.13*). Bases were scraped smooth to achieve rounded bottoms (*Figs. 14-16*). The potters' methods exemplify embodied knowledge—skills learnt through doing and seeing rather than formal instruction.

Figure 8: Mrs Pat Osaro kneads clay with her foot, mixing sand with the lumps of clay to open up the clay pores. The clay is then usable for forming small bowls. Uselu, Benin City.
Photo: Jean Borgatti, 10 November 2015.

(L) Figure 9: Mrs Pat Osaro forms clay bowls from lumps of kneaded clay. 10 November 2015.
(R) Figure 10: Removing formed bowl from plate used as base. Behind her, such freshly formed bowls are placed on a shelf to dry gradually, while dark brown fired bowls are stacked against the wall awaiting patrons. 12 November 2015. Uselu, Benin City. Photos: Jean Borgatti,

Figures 11-12: Mrs Patience Iziegbe forming clay pots.
Figure 13: Rounding up the pot's neck with a wet soft plantain leaf to get a near perfect finishing. Okabere, Benin City. Photos: Jean Borgatti, 30 November 2015.

(L) Figure 14: After beating, the exterior of the pot is scraped with sticks and pieces of plastic to smooth the surface and achieve the final shape. Mrs. Patience Iziegbe, Okabere, Benin City.
Photo: Jean Borgatti 30 November 2015.

(R) Figure 15: Finished pots have their bottoms scraped with a knife to achieve a rounded base after which they are placed in the sun to dry.

Figure 16: Close up - Excess clay being removed from the base of a finished pot with a knife. Madame Dora Onaiwu, Okabere, Benin City.
Photos: Jean Borgatti 30 November 2015.

Decorative techniques included the use of one roller made from fired clay to create designs (*Fig.17*), adding handles and traditional motifs such as representations linked to Olokun and Ogun with additional clay (*Figs.18&19*). Potters used various improvised tools including corn cobs and carved rollers to create impressions and patterns. These decorative marks added aesthetic value to the vessels and reflected cultural symbolism.

Figure 17: Mrs. Patience Iziegbe marks a pattern on the clay pot with a roller made of fired clay. Okabere, Benin City.
 Below: **Figures 18 &19:** Mrs. Patience Iziegbe adds external details to the shaped pot. Handles are decorative. Okabere, Benin City.
Photos Jean Borgatti 30 November 2015 .

Sun Drying

Shaped vessels were left under the sun to firm gradually, during which time decorative impressions stabilised. Once firm, pots were separated from their support shards (*Fig.10*), bases scraped (*Figs.14-16*), and vessels returned to the sun until thoroughly dried (*Figs. 20-22*).

(L) Figure 20: Sun baking the already scraped clay bowls to dry them in preparation for firing in an open bonfire (Mrs. Pat Osaro's Compound, Uselu, Benin City). 10 November 2015.

(R) Top-Figure 21: Clay pots drying in the sun, Okabere, Benin City. 26 November 2015.

(R) Bottom-Figure 22: Formed clay pots drying in the sun, allowing better results during firing. Okabere, Benin City. 6 July 2015, Photos Jean Borgatti

Baking Process

Firing occurred in open bonfires, typically during the dry season to reduce weather-related risks. The process involved two distinct stages:

1. **Pre-heating:** Grass and bamboo splits were piled lightly over pots for 10–15 minutes to gradually heat the pottery and reduce the risk of thermal shock.
2. **Final firing:** Hardwood was stacked densely around and above the pre-heated pots and ignited from all sides, producing steady flames for approximately one hour.

The two potter communities demonstrated different firing strategies. At Okabere, Mrs Patience Iziegbe employed multi-stage firing using corrugated iron sheets to regulate heat and maintain temperature, with pre-heating on bamboo racks placed three feet above ground (Figs. 23-31).

Figure 23: Mrs Patience Iziegbe uses the established tradition of pre-heating stacked pots on a bamboo rack. This is arranged about three feet above a light flame meant to dry the pots before subjecting them to more intense heat. **Figure 24:** Mrs Patience Iziegbe places corrugated iron sheets on top of the stacked pots to keep in the heat during pre-heating. Okabere, Benin City. *Photos: Jean Borgatti 9 July 2015.*

Figure 25: When the potters are satisfied that the pots are well dried, they unpack the pots from the bamboo rack ready for the final stage of the firing. **Figure 26:** The last stage of the firing process begins with the laying of bamboo splits on the leftover ashes from the preheating session to serve as a pad for the heated pots. Okabere, Benin City. *Photos: Jean Borgatti 9 July 2015.*

Figure 27: Bamboo splits continue to be layered around the pots to serve as ‘pads’ between them. Okabere, Benin City. **Figure 28:** The pile of pots is then surrounded with bamboo sticks arranged to form a conical shape. Okabere, Benin City. *Photos: Jean Borgatti 9 July 2015.*

Figure 29: The final bonfire is started by lighting the pile of sticks covering the pots on all sides, Okabere, Benin City. **Figure 30:** The bonfire on this occasion took about fifteen minutes to burn, completing the firing process. Okabere, Benin City. *Photos: Jean Borgatti 9 July 2015.*

Figure 31: The entire pile of bamboo sticks burns out completely to reveal the fired pots. Okabere, Benin City. *Photo: Jean Borgatti 9 July 2015.*

At Uselu, Mrs Pat Osaro chose to stack clay bowls in round formations for full open-air firing, a more direct approach suited to her market-oriented production schedule (Figs.32-36).

Figure 32: Mrs. Pat Osaro chooses to stack her clay bowls in the round for open firing. Uselu, Benin City. **Figure 33:** Stacked clay pots ready for bonfire. Uselu, Benin City. *Photos: Jean Borgatti 12 November 2015.*

Figure 34: Splits of dried wood are arranged vertically in and around the stacked clay bowls for firing. Uselu, Benin City. **Figure 35:** Open firing of pots at Uselu, Benin City. *Photos: Jean Borgatti 12 November 2015.*

Figure 36: Mrs Pat Osaro's fired clay bowls are stacked ready for the market. Uselu, Benin City. *Photo: Jean Borgatti 10 November 2015.*

Despite the expertise of the potters in handling the firing process, some losses were recorded; approximately five out of fifty pots cracked or exploded during firing. To mitigate this risk, potters controlled airflow using corrugated iron sheets as wind shields.

Surface Finishing

While pots were still hot, potters splashed on them a solution of ground turmeric mixed with a liquid consisting of water in which dried plantain or banana leaves had been soaked for two to three days. This produced a deep golden-tan tint (*Figs.37-39*). The turmeric wash sealed the pores of the fired pottery. Such finishing practices demonstrate the integration of local botanical knowledge into ceramic production. Beyond aesthetics, surface treatments are often linked to symbolic and ritual meanings in African pottery (Willett, 1971). In Benin, however, potters emphasised the practical role of turmeric as a sealing and colouring agent, highlighting the adaptive use of readily available materials.

Figure 37: Mrs. Patience Iziegbe grinds turmeric roots to prepare a wash used to seal the fired pots and give them a deep tan colour. **Figure 38 (R):** To make the turmeric wash solution, the potters soak dried plantain or banana leaves in water for two to three days, mixing the water with the ground turmeric. **Figure 39:** The baked pots are brought out from the fire and bathed while hot with the turmeric solution. Okabere, Benin City. *Photos: Jean Borgatti 9 July 2015.*

This process enhanced both aesthetic value and market appeal, allowing potters to command prices of approximately ₦1,250 per bowl in 2015.

Figure 40: Bathed pots are laid on the ground to cool before they are transported to the market. Okabere, Benin City. *Photo: Jean Borgatti 9 July 2015.*

Forms and Functions of Pots

Potters produced diverse wares serving multiple functions:

1. **Cooking pots:** Typically 7 inches in height with a 14-inch mouth diameter and 2 cm wall thickness, fired to approximately 750°C for earthenware durability.
2. **Storage pots:** 18 inches in height, 15 inches in diameter, designed as receptacles for household storage of grains and water.
3. **Market bowls:** 7 inches in diameter with smooth surface treatments, produced at approximately 200 pieces per season for sale in all major markets in Benin City.
4. **Ritual pots:** Associated with traditional deities such as Olokun and Ogun, incorporating traditional decorative motifs.

These forms reflected both functional adaptation and continuity of symbolic traditions deeply rooted in Benin culture.

Sustainability and Continuity of Pottery Practice

In Okabere, field observations in 2006 recorded four active potters in the community; by 2023, only two practitioners from the Onaiwu family remained active. In Uselu, there was already only one active potter in 2006, and by 2023 Mrs Pat Osaro continued as the sole practising potter documented in the community. The decline in practising potters reflects broader urbanisation trends and shifting economic priorities among younger generations, who increasingly prioritise metropolitan employment over craft-based livelihoods.

However, resourcefulness ensures continued relevance among rural consumers. Potters rely on locally available tools—leaves, husks, wood, and improvised implements—reducing production costs and enabling sustainable practices. The Onaiwu family lineage exemplifies matrilineal transmission of pottery knowledge, though transmission to the next generation remains uncertain. Mrs Pat Osaro, while highly skilled and productive (approximately 200 pieces per season), reports that none of her five children have engaged in pottery practice, representing a potential break in the transmission line.

DISCUSSION

The fieldwork carried out at the pottery sites of Okabere and Uselu illustrates both continuity and transformation within Benin's cultural landscape, viewed through the lenses of material culture, embodied practice, intangible cultural heritage, practice-led research, and the dynamics of continuity and adaptation.

Material Culture and Embodied Practice

Pottery in Benin exemplifies material culture as an extension of community identity. The vessels are not merely containers but artefacts embedded in social life, embodying resilience and adaptation (Miller, 2005). The embodied knowledge of potters demonstrates Bourdieu's (1977) concept of *habitus*—skills so ingrained that they become second nature, transmitted through years of apprenticeship and daily practice.

Intangible Cultural Heritage

The decline in potters highlights the vulnerability of intangible heritage. As Kurin (2004) notes, safeguarding requires community involvement and intergenerational transmission. Pottery in Okabere and Uselu reflects UNESCO's (2003) call for documentation and revitalisation of living traditions. Without intervention, this heritage risks extinction. The matrilineal transmission of knowledge from mothers to daughters, as seen in the Onaiwu family, is a core mechanism of this intangible heritage. Its disruption due to urbanisation represents not just an economic shift but a potential severing of a vital cultural chain.

Practice-led Research

The collaborative approach—between practitioner and historian—illustrates the value of practice-led research in the arts. By engaging with clay processes first-hand, the study generated insights inaccessible through textual research alone. This aligns with Candy and Edmonds' (2018) argument that creative practice can itself be a form of research inquiry.

Further reflections on the relationship between potters, ritual practice, and contemporary Benin shrines are developed in a separate study by Borgatti and Eweka (2024).

Continuity and Adaptation

The continuity observed in techniques is not merely a matter of decades but is part of a millennia-long lineage dating back to the Ogiso period, making its present-day adaptation all the more significant. Women remain the custodians of this craft, transmitting knowledge through matrilineal lines (Ekpo, 2013; Osariyekemwen & Eweka, 2016). While industrial containers have displaced many traditional uses, ritual and symbolic functions persist. Furthermore, potters' resourceful use of discarded household items as tools exemplifies sustainability and low-cost innovation. Resourcefulness is evident in the use of simple, locally available tools and organic finishing agents. At the same time, urbanisation and alternative livelihoods have reduced the viability of pottery as a primary occupation (Akinbogun, 2012). What survives is partly due to the resilience of dedicated families, but the craft faces existential threats.

CONCLUSION

This study demonstrates that pottery in Okabere and Uselu communities represents both continuity and decline: continuity in techniques, symbolism, and resilience, but decline in the number of practitioners and economic viability. By situating pot making within discourses of material culture, intangible heritage, and practice-led research, while also tracing its historical depth and gendered socio-cultural roots, the article underscores its significance as both cultural heritage and contemporary practice.

By aligning detailed process documentation with comparative African pottery scholarship, the study offers both empirical and interpretive evidence for understanding the pressures on women's craft traditions under contemporary socio-economic change.

Safeguarding requires deliberate intervention: integrating pottery into art curricula, documenting oral histories, supporting potters through cooperatives, and exploring new markets for traditional wares. Tourism interest in these practices is evident, and cultural institution collaborations could provide sustainable pathways. Pottery is more than a craft—it is a living archive of Benin's history, identity, and creative imagination. The practices documented here stand as living heritage, linking contemporary Benin to its Ogiso-era past and offering pedagogical and creative value in contemporary art education and cultural policy.

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